

Design and Construction of the Stridsberg Bridge

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ABSTRACT

The Stridsberg Bridge (Stridsbergsbron) is a new 255 m long road- and pedestrian bridge spanning the Göta canal in Trollhättan, Sweden. It was inaugurated in June 2023, and consists of two composite approach bridges and a moveable double bascule bridge over the navigational channel.

The single span East Approach Bridge (EAB) is 20.5 m long and consists of hot-rolled steel sections with an in-situ cast concrete slab on top. To reduce sagging moments, a moment connection is established between the east side concrete abutment and the superstructure. The bridge was established by lifting steel beams into place, before in-situ casting of the concrete slab.

The West Approach Bridge (WAB) has three spans and a total length of 147 m. The longest span is 57.5 m. Its composite cross-section is built-up of an orthotropic trapezoidal steel section with an in-situ cast concrete slab on top. The steel part of the WAB superstructure was erected by incremental launching . After launching the concrete slab was sequentially casted in-situ.

The movable bridge (MOV) is Sweden's largest double bascule bridge, with a total length of 49.6 m between the pivots and a free clearance width of 35 m for ship passage. The bascule leaves are constructed in steel and consists of two box sections with an orthotropic steel deck. They were transported to site in three pieces, before being welded together. Installation into the bascule chambers was performed by backwards launching the leaves from a barge on the waterside into the bascule chambers where they subsequentially were lowered into place.

In this paper, the main features of the structural system is presented, together with the design and construction of the bridge.

Keywords: Composite bridge, Movable bridge, Steel design, Construction, Incremental launching

1 INTRODUCTION

The Stridsberg Bridge (Stridsbergsbron in native Swedish) is a new 255 m long bridge crossing the Göta canal in Trollhättan, Sweden. It is comprised of the composite West Approach Bridge (WAB), the double bascule Moveable bridge (MOV) and the composite East Approach Bridge (EAB), refer Fig 1. The bridge is founded on bedrock either directly or on bored steel piles.

3 THE WEST APPROACH BRIDGE

Spanning between the western riverbank and the west bascule chamber, the WAB provides access to the top of the bascule chamber. The bridge is 147.2 m long, divided into three spans with a length of 57.5 m, 57.5 m and 32.2 m. The substructure consists of from west, an abutment (support 1), two piers (support 2 and 3), and a corbel on the bascule chamber (support 4). The superstructure is supported by two POT bearings at each support line.

The supports 1 and 3 are founded on short bored steel piles, with a diameter of 219 mm. Support 2 is founded on high piling, with the pile cap established just below the water level elevated above the riverbed, with piles being approx. 30 m long, with a diameter of 610 mm.

The superstructure is realized as a composite section, consisting of a trapezoidal orthotropic steel section with a concrete slab on top refer fig 3. In the centre of the section a welded I-girder is positioned supported by the internal bracing system. This is introduced to reduce transverse bending moments in the slab. At the supports, the internal bracing system is replaced by a full-plated diaphragm.

Fig. 3. Cross-section of the west approach bridge superstructure.

3.1 Design and analysis

To accurately analyse the behaviour of the bridge, a global finite element model was established using beam elements in the commercial software SOFiSTiK for all parts of the Stridsberg bridge. For local design checks, design of the slab and for establishing bracing forces in the superstructure, global hybrid models, where part of the superstructure was modelled using shell elements, were used, refer Fig 4a).

Fig. 4. a) Global hybrid model. b) SBD model.

The general design was performed in accordance with the Eurocodes, together with the Swedish national annexes and “Krav Brobyggande”. The longitudinal design of the superstructure was performed using the In-house Ramboll software SBD, refer Fig 4b). This is a strong software for treating arbitrary steel and composite class 4 cross-sections, with a proven track record, refer (1) and (2). When performing the design, the internal I-girder was neglected. This, as there were no top plan bracings present during construction and concrete casting, as of why the I-girder first would attract stresses, when the concrete slab had hardened. Instead, the internal I-girder was designed based on section forces, established from the global hybrid models, considering the casting sequence of the concrete slab.

The statical system, with a short span between supports (3) and (4) together with torsional rotation, meant that uplift was seen at end support (4). To avoid lift at this support, the girder was designed with a global camber with a height of ~450 mm. In this way vertical reaction load could be redistributed from the piers (2) and (3) to the end supports, see Fig 5.

Fig. 5. Global camber for prestressing and reaction redistribution. The blue line (-) represents the moment curve.

3.2 Construction

The superstructure (both WAB, MOV & EAB) was welded by AB Bröderna Jansson in Halmstad, see Fig 6a). To accommodate truck transportation, the steel section was divided into 12 segments. Longitudinally it was divided into 6 pieces, which were all divided at the middle of the section. This to accommodate width and length requirements for tuck transportation, refer Fig 6b). The segments were then welded together at site and placed on a launching bed.

a)

b)

Fig. 6. a) Welding of girder at Workshop (Courtesy: PEAB). b) Central splitting of girder for transportation.

The bridge was incrementally launched with a 16.3 m long launching nose in 4 stages, with the formwork installed, by AB Jinert. It was launched in a lifted position, with an upwards slope. At the supports, launching bearings were placed on jacks, to accommodate large downwards movements, caused e.g. by the curvature of the bridge due to the global camber.

Fig. 7. Launching of the west approach bridge steel girder (Courtesy: PEAB).

To avoid having the incremental launch governing the thickness of the bottom plate, following measures were introduced:

- 1. At supports 1 and 2, a total of four launching bearings were used, two in each longitudinal direction. The bearings were placed on hydraulic jacks, ensuring equal vertical reactions on the four bearings. This was done, to reduce the vertical reaction on each bearing, as well as increasing the effective transverse load bearing length on the web.*
- 2. The launching bearings was designed such that they could resist the concentrated load directly under the web plates. This meant that the system wasn't dependent on the bottom plates capability of spreading out the vertical reaction through plate bending. This meant, that the only force the bottom plate had to be designed for was the horizontal component, resulting from the web plate being inclined.*

After the incremental launch, the concrete slab was sequentially casted. An effort was made to avoid plan cross bracings attached to the top flange, as this will usually lead to fatigue sensitive details. To avoid this, a detailed FE-model of the girder was established using shell elements, see Figure 8a), and each of the casting stages was implemented. Based on this model, critical buckling factors was established, and the buckling resistance calculated. On Figure 8b) the concrete casting of the deck slab is shown.

a)

b)

Fig. 8. a) FE-model for analysing top flange buckling during concrete casting. b) Sequential concrete casting of the deck slab on the WAB.

4 THE MOVABLE BRIDGE

The moveable bridge is Sweden's largest double bascule with a span between pivots just shy of 50 m, and a free navigational channel width of 35 m, refer Fig 9.

Fig. 9. Moveable bridge (Courtesy: PEAB).

The bascule is hydraulically operated with two vertical cylinders to manoeuvre the bridge. The bridge and machinery is dimensioned to be able to operate with a single cylinder if needed. The bascule is supported on negative fixed bearings in the back (heel), rotational bearings at the pivot and shear locks where the two noses meet, refer Fig 10. Rear shear locks are placed at the heel and there are provisions to park the leaf in an open position if needed.

The leaves are ballasted with high density concrete (3800 kg/m³) in an enclosed steel section at the heel, as well as adjustable steel blocks for modifications and fine tuning.

Fig. 10. Bascule leaf 3D assembly underside.

The carriageway comprises of two traffic lanes and two large pedestrian/bicycle lanes, positioned at each side of the bridge. The bridge deck is built and designed so that the pedestrian lanes can be removed so traffic can be accommodated on the entire deck if needed in the future.

4.1 Design and analysis

The design of a moveable bridge poses unique challenges compared to static bridges as it is partly a bridge and partly a machine. The design was inspired by several similar bridges from the past from Sweden and abroad.

Fig. 11. View of the global FEM model showing the MOV.

The steel leaves are made up of two closed box girders over its entire length, with an orthotropic bridge deck in the front and a ballast box in the rear. The MOV was modelled as a full shell model (see Fig 11) and incorporated into the global bridge model for the entire bridge. The primary ULS design of the steel leaves were performed using the effective section method for the main girders and cross girders where beam behaviour could be assumed. Where that wasn't the case, individual areas and plates were designed using the reduced stress method based on shell model results directly. Consequently, a full shell model was deemed necessary to properly model and capture local SLS stresses and to design for fatigue. Fatigue design was performed using rain flow counting with stresses from traffic and various scenarios, such as bridge opening, had to be combined at multiple locations.

The leaves main supports are realized through 600 mm diameter forged rotational axles made from the commonly used 34CrNiMo6 alloy. They are supported by spherical rotational plain bearings resting in a custom-made bearing housing, designed specifically for this bridge. Other contact points, such as the front shear lock and the negative bearings, are made from duplex stainless steel mated against bronze alloy bearings, to increase durability of the exposed elements that cannot be painted. The front shear locks are operated by electromechanical actuators with a capacity of 70 kN each, where the smaller rear shear locks are operated by a small hydraulic cylinder. The steel leaves were modelled in full detail in a 3D BIM model to ensure proper balancing of the bridge, as well as enabling drawing production.

4.2 Construction

The concrete bascule chambers were constructed in the river be means of a cofferdam, resting on bored steel piles into the bedrock. The bascule leaves were constructed in a workshop off site in 7 sections, to enable transportation. They were then transported to an assembly yard just north of the bridge location for final assembly and testing. Once the leaves were ready, they were launched unto a barge, resting on 4 individual towers. The barge then sailed the leaves in front of the bascule chamber, where the whole bascule leaf was launched backwards into the chamber. The geometry required that the leaves were tilted backwards by a few degrees just before reaching their final resting place. Once in place, the rotational bearings were bolted onto the concrete columns, and the leaves freed from the barge. Ballast concrete was cast into the ballast box and subsequently the adjustable ballast was installed, and the hydraulic cylinders connected to the leaves.

Fig. 12. Backwards launching of bascule leaves into chamber (Courtesy: Jinert).

5 THE EAST APPROACH BRIDGE

The connection between the east bank and the east bascule chamber was established through the 21.2 m long East Approach Bridge (EAB). It is a single span composite bridge, composed of 10 hot-rolled HE sections with a concrete slab on top. The superstructure is supported by elastomeric bearings at the bascule chamber placed on corbels. On the east side the superstructure is casted together with a concrete abutment wall, founded directly on the bedrock. The bridge is spanning over a single railway track. Elevation and cross-section of the bridge is shown in Fig 13.

Fig. 13. East approach bridge. a) Elevation. b) Cross-section.

5.1 Design, analysis, and construction

For the EAB it was important to keep the superstructure height at a minimum, while still respecting the clearance profile underneath the bridge. This, as an increase of structural height would affect quantities in all other elements of the collective bridge. To achieve this, following structural measures were introduced:

1. An integral connection with the abutment wall was created, to reduce sagging moments in the span, refer Figure 14b).
2. Two temporary supports underneath the hot-rolled steel girders were planned, to ensure a greater part of the permanent loads were carried by the composite section, refer Figure 14a).

This led to a span to height ratio of 25, as well as ensuring hot-rolled steel profiles could be used, instead of welded girders.

Fig. 14. a) Temporary supports during concrete casting. b) Integral connection between composite girders and concrete abutment wall.

The analysis was performed in the commercial software SOFiSTiK, refer Figure 15. Here longitudinal behaviour was captured through longitudinal beam elements, with steel composite section properties. Transversely, the beam elements were connected with shell elements simulating the concrete slab. The shell elements were modelled without any axial and longitudinal flexural

stiffness, to only capture the transverse behaviour and transverse load spreading ability. The model included a precise interpretation of the construction sequence, through the program module CSM in SOFiSTiK, ensuring locked-in steel stresses in the composite sections was accurately considered.

Fig. 15. Global model EAB.

Design of the composite beams was performed in the commercial software Ponti EC4, with the deck slab and concrete abutment designed using the program module BEMESS in SOFiSTiK.

6 OTHER STRUCTURES

At the navigational channel, ship protection structures are established to protect the bascule chambers. For ship traffic traveling towards Göteborg a caisson is protecting the west bascule chamber. The caisson is constructed out of concrete with precast elements and filled with soil. For ship traffic traveling towards Vänern a fender structure (ledverk) is constructed to minimize the risk for ship collision with the bascule chambers. The structures are shown on Figure 16.

a)

b)

Fig. 16. a) Caisson. b) Fender structures.

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